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An analysis of the dynamical behaviour of systems with fractional damping for Mechanical Engineering applications

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Abstract: Fractional derivative models are widely used to easily characterise more complex damping behaviour than the viscous one, although the underlying properties are not trivial. Several studies about the mathematical properties can be found, but are usually far from the most daily applications. Thus, this paper studies the properties of structural systems whose damping is represented by a fractional model from the point of view of a mechanical engineer. First, a single-degree-of-freedom system with fractional damping is analysed. Specifically, the distribution of the poles and the dynamic response to several excitations is studied for different model parameter values highlighting dissimilarities from systems with conventional viscous damping. In fact, thanks to fractional models, particular behaviours are observed that cannot be reproduced by classical ones. Finally, the dynamics of a machine shaft supported by two bearings presenting fractional damping is analysed. The study is carried out by the Finite Element method, deriving in a system with symmetric matrices. Eigenvalues and eigenvectors are obtained by means of an iterative method, and the effect of damping is visualised on the mode shapes. Besides, the response to a perturbation is computed, revealing the influence of the model parameters on the resulting vibration.

Keywords: fractional damping; vibration; dynamic behaviour

1. Introduction

In the context of dynamics, fractional models allow to represent easily the vibratory behaviour of elements that would otherwise require complex formulations, such as multielement or hereditary models, because they are able to reproduce correctly the damping mechanisms that come into play using a low number of variables [1,2]. Fractional models are specially advantageous for polymeric materials that show some level of dependence to frequency and arise naturally, for example, from certain motions of Newtonian fluids [3] or the molecular theories that predict the behaviour of certain type of polymeric materials [4].

Several works treating the behaviour of dynamic systems following fractional models from a mathematical perspective can be found in the literature. For instance, in [5], a fractionally damped single-degree-of-freedom (1 DOF) oscillator was analysed using the Laplace transform. It was found that a system of this kind exhibits nine distinct behaviour cases in opposition to the three shown by a traditional oscillator. Also, in the [6–8] series, the behaviour of a fractional oscillator whose derivative order was between one and two was studied, first when subjected to initial conditions and, after, when applying a sinusoidal force to the system. The main conclusion of the series was that a fractional oscillator like the one analysed presented damping even if not explicitly stated.

Computing methods have been widely proposed as well, mostly numerical [9] due to the difficulty to obtain closed-form solutions. Apart from the Laplace transform, that has been already mentioned,

the Fourier transform [4], an eigenvector expansion in the state space [10], modal synthesis [11] or finite elements [12,13] have been used to obtain the response of systems presenting fractional damping.

In general, this type of systems are not analysed from the engineering point of view, even if fractional models have been used in the actual engineering practice, for instance, to linearise equations or to reduce the number of parameters needed to represent elastoplastic [14] or viscoelastic behaviours [15]. For this reason, the objective of this work is to shed light on the dynamic behaviour of a system whose damping is modelled using a fractional model. To this aim, first the theoretical background is presented with the aid of a 1 DOF system, for which the distribution of poles is studied and whose dynamic response to different excitations is computed. Instead of focusing on obtaining the analytical response for certain values, the behaviour of the system is analysed numerically in a range of values in order to identify trends. The goal is to identify the differences between a system whose damping is modelled as fractional and one following a traditional viscous damping formulation. This understanding is used afterwards to represent the dynamics of a machine shaft supported by two bearings with fractional damping.

2. Theoretical background: a 1 DOF system with fractional damping

A single-degree-of-freedom mechanical system that presents fractional damping follows the equation of motion

$$m\ddot{x} + cD^\alpha x + kx = F(t) / \alpha \in [0,1], \quad (1)$$

where m , c and k are respectively the mass, damping and stiffness of the system, $F(t)$ is an external force and α is the order of the fractional derivative that, in order to describe a viscoelastic damper, is considered to be between zero and one — if the order of the derivative were zero, the damper would behave as a spring and would be considered “elastic”; if one, the damping would be viscous.

The fractional derivative of a function $f(t)$ is computed following the Caputo definition using the gamma function Γ as

$$D^\alpha f(t) = \frac{d^\alpha f(t)}{dt^\alpha} = \frac{1}{\Gamma(n-\alpha)} \frac{d}{dt} \int_0^t \frac{f^{(n)}(u)}{(t-u)^{\alpha+1-n}} du, \quad (2)$$

where $n-1 \leq \alpha < n$. In this work, the Caputo definition is preferred to the Riemman-Liouville because the constant terms produced by the Laplace transform of the former have direct physical meaning [5] whereas the interpretation of such terms in the latter is more complex [16].

In the case under study, as the order of the derivative α is between zero and one and, in consequence, $n = 1$, the fractional derivative in (2) becomes

$$D^\alpha f(t) = \frac{d^\alpha f(t)}{dt^\alpha} = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \frac{d}{dt} \int_0^t \frac{f(u)}{(t-u)^\alpha} du. \quad (3)$$

For more detail about the definition or computation of fractional derivatives, any of the classical texts on the subject [2,17–19] is recommended.

2.1. Poles of the system

One of the peculiarities of a system with fractional damping is the nature of its poles. In order to compute them, (1) is expressed in the Laplace domain, where adopts the form

$$(ms^2 + cs^\alpha + k) X(s) = s^{\alpha-1} x(0), \quad (4)$$

if $F(t) = 0$ is considered, $X(s) = \mathcal{L}\{x(t)\}$ being the Laplace transform of the displacement $x(t)$. Then, the characteristic equation

$$ms^2 + cs^\alpha + k = 0 \quad (5)$$

69 is solved. Supposing that α is a rational number and can be therefore expressed as the quotient of two
 70 integers $\alpha = p/q$, (5) becomes the polynomial of order $2q$

$$mr^{2q} + cr^p + k = 0 / r = s^{\frac{1}{q}} \quad (6)$$

71 from which the poles of the system can be obtained.

72 From (6), one could think that a fractionally damped system has $2q$ poles but, in reality, only two
 73 of them — a complex conjugate pair [5], actually — are solutions to the original system (5), the rest are
 74 extraneous solutions due to the solving process.

75 The fact that (5) has only two complex conjugate poles can be explained from the physics of the
 76 real system it models: a 1 DOF system can only vibrate at a single frequency. Also, the fact that the
 77 poles of the system are complex conjugates implies that the response is always oscillatory and that
 78 there are no overdamped or critically damped cases as defined for a traditional 1 DOF system [10].
 79 This feature of systems with fractional damping will be further discussed when studying its dynamic
 80 response in Section 2.2.

81 In order to better understand the behaviour of the system, the variation in the position of the poles
 82 with the order of the derivative α is studied. Without loss of generality, for the numerical computations
 83 the mass m , damping c and stiffness k parameters are considered unitary (in any coherent system of
 84 units) while the value of the order of the derivative α ranges between zero and one, the completely
 85 elastic and the completely viscoelastic behaviours respectively.

86 If the poles of the system for different values of α are plotted in the complex plane, the shape
 87 shown in Figure 1 is obtained. In it, the solutions obtained from the variable change in (6) are shown
 88 in black while the ones that satisfy (5) are highlighted in red.

Figure 1. Distribution of poles for different values of α . The solutions that comply with (5) are highlighted in red.

89 For every value of α , the centroid of each of the two distributions shown in Figure 1 computed as

$$C = \frac{1}{q} \sum_{j=1}^q s_j, \quad (7)$$

90 s_j being the j th pole of the system and q the amount of solutions of (6) for each distribution, the
 91 extraneous ones included, fall in $\pm\omega_0 = \pm\sqrt{k/m}$.

92 Another conclusion that can be drawn from the variation of the position of the poles with the
 93 value α is that, contrary to what could be expected, the number of decimal positions used to express α
 94 and, thus, the p and q values used to approximate it as a rational number, do not affect the position of
 95 the poles. This means that considering α or a slightly perturbed value $\alpha + \delta$ provides the same results
 96 both in terms of poles and, in consequence, of time response.

97 Then, the relationship of the damped frequency of the system, represented by the imaginary part
 98 of the poles, with the order of the derivative is studied. As shown in Figure 2, the damped frequency
 99 of the system ranges from

$$\omega_d = \sqrt{\frac{k+c}{m}} \quad (8)$$

100 when $\alpha = 0$ (it should be noted that in this case, as the damper behaves like a spring, the system will be
 101 *undamped*) to the well known formula for the viscous case when $\alpha = 1$

$$\omega_d = \omega_0 \sqrt{1 - \zeta^2}, \quad (9)$$

102 where $\zeta = c/(2\sqrt{km})$ and $\omega_0 = \sqrt{k/m}$. The damped frequency decays with the order of the derivative
 103 α because, due to the viscoelastic nature of the model, the lower this order, a bigger part of the damping
 104 behaves as stiffness [20].

Figure 2. Evolution of damped frequency ω_d with the order of the derivative α . The mass, stiffness and damping parameters are unitary. The damped frequency ranges from $\omega_d = \sqrt{\frac{k+c}{m}} = \sqrt{2}$ to $\omega_d = \omega_0 \sqrt{1 - \zeta^2} = 0.866$.

105 Then, the value of the damping parameter c is changed keeping the order of the fractional
 106 derivative constant, in order to study the evolution of the damped frequency. In contrast to what
 107 happens in systems with viscous damping, increasing the damping parameter c in a fractionally
 108 damped system increases the vibration frequency. This can be explained again by the viscoelastic
 109 nature of fractional damping: while in a system with viscous damping a change in the value of the
 110 damping parameter c does not affect the stiffness; if the damping is fractional, both magnitudes are
 111 interrelated and an increase in the damping parameter c also stiffens the system.

Figure 3. Evolution of the damped frequency ω_d with the damping parameter c for different values of the order of the derivative α .

112 2.2. Dynamic response

113 Another aspect in which a system with fractional damping differs from one showing viscous
114 damping is the dynamic response. This differences are analysed in the 1 DOF system, first, when it is
115 subjected to initial conditions and, after, when a impulse or step force is applied.

116 In order to compute the value of the fractional derivative for a given time t , the Grünwald-Letnikov
117 method is used for the numerical computations. Its objective is to take advantage of the definition of
118 the derivative and approximate the gamma functions with some recursively computed coefficients.
119 The derivative of order α is, thus, expressed as

$$D^\alpha f(t) = \lim_{\Delta t \rightarrow 0} \left(\frac{1}{(\Delta t)^\alpha} \sum_{j=0}^{S-1} \frac{\Gamma(j-\alpha)}{\Gamma(-\alpha)\Gamma(j+1)} f(t-j\Delta t) \right) \quad (10)$$

120 where $S = t/\Delta t$ is the number of samples. Considering

$$A_{j+1} = \frac{\Gamma(j-\alpha)}{\Gamma(-\alpha)\Gamma(j+1)}, \quad (11)$$

121 the A_j coefficients can be computed recursively by

$$A_1 = 1, \quad (12)$$

$$A_{j+1} = \frac{j-\alpha-1}{j} A_j \quad (13)$$

122 and the derivative of order α takes the simplified form

$$D^\alpha f(t) \approx \frac{1}{(\Delta t)^\alpha} \sum_{j=0}^{S-1} A_{j+1} f(t-j\Delta t), \quad (14)$$

123 which can be easily introduced in a numerical method, a forward Euler in this case.

124 It should be noted that fractional operators are convolution integrals and, as such, they have
125 memory, making it is necessary to store the previous history so as to be able to compute the response
126 in a certain step [1]. If needed, techniques as the one described in [20] could be used to reduce the
127 storing requirements.

128 The presented methodology is followed in the next sections to compute the response of the
 129 fractionally damped 1 DOF system under study to initial conditions and to a impulse and step force,
 130 two of the most typical excitations.

131 2.2.1. Response to initial conditions

132 The response of a fractionally damping system whose m , c and k parameters are unitary and
 133 subjected to the initial conditions $\{x_0, v_0\} = \{1, 0\}$ is shown in Figure 4. As predicted from the poles
 134 of the system, the response is oscillatory and decays in time.

Figure 4. Time response of a fractionally damped system for different values of the order of the derivative.

135 The main difference that a system with fractional damping presents in comparison to one that
 136 shows viscous damping regarding its response to initial conditions is the appearance of a non oscillatory
 137 term that decays in time [9]. This effect can be seen in Figure 5, where the response in the frequency
 138 domain, obtained by the Fast Fourier Transform of the time response, is represented for different
 139 values of the order of derivative α . During the initial part of the response (Figure 5 (a)), only a peak
 140 at the vibration frequency can be noticed; in the final part of the decay (Figure 5 (b)), however, it is
 141 possible to identify also a peak in the spectrum at zero frequency, that is related to the non oscillatory
 142 term, together with the peak at the vibration frequency.

143 From a physical point of view, the appearance of a non oscillatory term has two implications. First,
 144 it means that the equilibrium position of the system is not constant but it varies with time. Taking into
 145 account that the equilibrium position is defined by the mass and the stiffness of the system and, in this
 146 case, the mass is constant, the single explanation to this phenomenon is that the stiffness of the system
 147 varies with time. Secondly, it implies that the system does not oscillate with decreasing amplitude
 148 until it finally stops, but that it reaches a point in which it approaches the original equilibrium position
 149 without oscillating.

150 Another aspect in which a system with fractional damping differs from one with viscous damping
 151 is in the fact that a critical damping ratio in which the system does not oscillate around the equilibrium
 152 position cannot be defined [10,20]. The response always crosses the origin of coordinates at least once
 153 due to the nature of the poles of the system, that are always complex conjugates. For this reason,
 154 fractional damping allows to model dampers whose response only crosses the equilibrium position a
 155 single time, a case that cannot be represented with accuracy using a traditional model. For example,
 156 the 1 DOF system under study presents this behaviour when the damping parameter $c = 2$ and the
 157 order of the derivative $\alpha = 0.9$ (Figure 6).

Figure 5. Response of a fractionally damped system in the frequency domain: (a) from $t = 0$ to $t = 20$, (b) for $t > 20$.

Figure 6. Response of a 1 DOF fractionally damped system with unitary mass and stiffness parameters, the order of the derivative being $\alpha = 0.9$ and the damping parameter $c = 2$ when subjected to initial conditions $\{x_0, v_0\} = \{1, 0\}$.

158 2.2.2. Response to impulse

159 The response to an impulse is of interest because it provides a way to define critical damping.
 160 According to [10], critical damping can be defined for systems with fractional damping as the value
 161 for which the response is tangent to the axis of zero displacement when an impulse force

$$F(t) = \begin{cases} 1/\Delta t, & 0 < t < \Delta t \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

162 is applied to the system. This means that for values of damping greater than this the response does not
 163 change sign, even if it still oscillates, around a position that varies with time in this case (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Difference between an overdamped systems with viscous or fractional damping.

164 Following this reasoning, the value of critical damping can be estimated for different values of
 165 the order of the derivative α . For example, in Figure 8, the response of the 1 DOF system with unitary
 166 mass and stiffness parameters and critical damping when subjected to a impulse is presented. For low
 167 values of α the response always changes sign no matter how high the added damping: increasing the
 168 damping parameter makes the system stiffer and the effect of the increase in the natural frequency is
 169 greater than that of the dissipation.

Figure 8. Response to impulse of a system with critical damping for different values of the order of the derivative α .

170 2.2.3. Response to step

171 The response of the system with fractional damping to a step force

$$F(t) = \begin{cases} 0, & t < 0 \\ 1, & 0 \leq t \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

172 has the peculiarity that it stays under the response of a system with viscous damping. As an example,
 173 the response of the 1 DOF of freedom system with unitary mass, damping and stiffness constants under
 174 study is presented in Figure 9 depending of the order of the derivative α for a unit step excitation. It
 175 can be noted that for systems with fractional damping the overshoot decreases but the settling time is
 176 much longer, specially when decreasing the value of the order of the derivative.

Figure 9. Response to step for different values of α .

177 3. Application: bearing support

178 In order to illustrate the properties of the fractional models presented in the previous sections in a
 179 real life application, a shaft supported by one bearing in each end is considered. The shaft is modelled
 180 by means of beam finite elements; both supports, following the typical model of a bearing [21], as a
 181 combination of a spring and fractional damper (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Shaft supported by a bearing in each end, where N stands for the number of degrees of freedom of the finite element model of the shaft. The bearing support affects the $(N - 1)$ th degree of freedom, as the N th is related to the rotation of the end.

182 For the numerical application, a shaft of length $L = 1$ m and circular section of diameter $d = 0.4$ m
 183 made of steel with a Young's modulus of $E = 210$ GPa and density $\rho = 7900$ kg/m³ is considered.
 184 The natural frequencies, mode shapes and response of the shaft when changing the parameters of
 185 the bearings are studied, the two bearings being identical ($k_1 = k_{N-1} = k$, $c_1 = c_{N-1} = c$ and
 186 $\alpha_1 = \alpha_{N-1} = \alpha$).

187 3.1. Natural frequencies and mode shapes

188 The eigenpairs of a the shaft supported by bearings that present fractional damping satisfy the
 189 relationship

$$\left(-\lambda_r^* \mathbf{M} + \mathbf{K}_{\text{shaft}} + \mathbf{K}_{\text{supp}}^*(\omega_r)\right) \boldsymbol{\phi}_r^* = \mathbf{0}, \quad (17)$$

190 where λ_r^* and $\boldsymbol{\phi}_r^*$ are respectively the eigenvalue and the eigenvector of the r th mode, \mathbf{M} the mass
 191 matrix of the system, that corresponds to the mass matrix of the shaft as the supports are considered
 192 massless, $\mathbf{K}_{\text{shaft}}$ and $\mathbf{K}_{\text{supp}}^*(\omega)$ the stiffness matrices of the shaft and the bearing supports. This last
 193 complex matrix $\mathbf{K}_{\text{supp}}^*(\omega)$ is frequency dependent and is defined as

$$\mathbf{K}_{\text{supp}}^*(\omega) = \sum_{j \in B} (k_j + c_j (i\omega)^\alpha) \mathbf{e}_j \mathbf{e}_j^T / B = \{1, N-1\}, \quad (18)$$

194 where B holds the positions of the bearing supports, in this case the first and penultimate $(N-1)$ degrees
 195 of freedoms, the ones that represent the vertical displacement of the first and last nodes, respectively

196 and \mathbf{e}_j stands for the unit vector that corresponds to the j th degree of freedom. As the matrix \mathbf{K}_{supp} is
 197 frequency dependent, an iterative method is needed to obtain the eigenpairs of the system: the reader
 198 can find the details in [22,23].

199 With the aim of studying the evolution of the vibration frequencies of the system with the order
 200 of the derivative α , the values of the stiffness and damping parameters of the bearing supports are set
 201 to $k = 10^4$ N/m and $c = 50$ N s $^\alpha$ /m respectively. When the shaft is discretised with 60 beam elements
 202 in its length the results shown in Figure 11 are obtained. It can be observed that, as deduced for the
 203 1 DOF system, changing the order of the derivative affects the stiffness of the supports and, thus, the
 204 vibration frequencies.

Figure 11. Evolution of the frequency of the first two modes with the order of the derivative α .

205 Another aspect that should be taken into account regarding the eigenpairs is that the modes are
 206 complex due to the non-proportionality of the damping. When the value of the damping parameter c
 207 is low this effect is barely noticeable so, for the sake of clarity, its value is increased to $c = 1000$ N s $^\alpha$ /m
 208 in the computation of the mode shapes presented in Figure 12. The phase of the mode shape in each
 209 point of the shaft is represented with the aim of bringing to light the complex nature of the modes: if
 210 the mode were normal, the phase would change abruptly from $-\pi$ to π (or vice versa) in the nodal
 211 points, but it is not what occurs.

212 It should be noted also that the mode shapes are not affected by the order of the derivative α but
 213 the complex nature of the modes is more acute for high values of α as the effect of the damping is
 214 higher.

215 3.2. Dynamic response

216 Next, the time response of the shaft to a perturbation from the base is computed following the
 217 procedure in [24] by means of a **M-C-K** Newmark method. The details of the implementation of such
 218 method can be found in [12], but, in short, it consists in expressing the equation of motion of the system
 219 in the instant $n + 1$ as

$$\mathbf{M}\ddot{\mathbf{u}}_{n+1} + \mathbf{C}(D^\alpha \mathbf{u})_{n+1} + \mathbf{K}\mathbf{u}_{n+1} = \mathbf{F}_{n+1}, \quad (19)$$

220 and introducing the notation

$$\mathbf{M}\ddot{\mathbf{u}}_{n+1} + \bar{\mathbf{C}}\dot{\mathbf{u}}_{n+1} + \mathbf{K}\mathbf{u}_{n+1} = \bar{\mathbf{F}}_{n+1}, \quad (20)$$

221 where

$$\bar{\mathbf{C}} = (\Delta t)^{1-\alpha} \mathbf{C} \quad (21)$$

Figure 12. First five mode shapes of the supported shaft: real part and phase.

222 and

$$\bar{\mathbf{F}}_{n+1} = \mathbf{F}_{n+1} - \frac{1}{(\Delta t)^\alpha} \mathbf{C} \left[\mathbf{u}_n + \sum_{j=1}^n A_{j+1} \mathbf{u}_{n+1-j} \right] \quad (22)$$

223 in order to use the Grünwald-Letnikov definition of the fractional derivative in the computations. In
 224 the case under study the mass matrix \mathbf{M} is that of the shaft; the stiffness matrix \mathbf{K} is the sum of the one
 225 of the shaft and the one of the supports

$$\mathbf{K} = \mathbf{K}_{\text{shaft}} + \mathbf{K}_{\text{supp}} \quad (23)$$

226 where

$$\mathbf{K}_{\text{supp}} = \sum_{j \in B} k_j \mathbf{e}_j \mathbf{e}_j^\top / B = \{1, N-1\}, \quad (24)$$

227 and the damping matrix \mathbf{C} is given by the damping of the bearing supports as

$$\mathbf{C} = \sum_{j \in B} c_j \mathbf{e}_j \mathbf{e}_j^\top / B = \{1, N-1\}. \quad (25)$$

228 The time response of the supported shaft to a seismic excitation is computed as follows: first,
 229 the static response to a displacement of the rightmost end is computed; then, it is introduced into the
 230 presented Newmark scheme as an initial deformation \mathbf{u}_0 . Four distinct cases are studied:

- 231 • **Case 1:** a viscous case ($\alpha = 1$) with low stiffness ($k_{\text{ref}} = 10^4$ N/m) and low damping ($c_{\text{ref}} =$
 232 50 N s/m) that is used for reference, in which the rigid body movement prevails.
- 233 • **Case 2:** a viscous case ($\alpha = 1$) with low stiffness ($k = k_{\text{ref}}$) and supercritical damping ($c = 10c_{\text{ref}}$),
 234 in which the shaft returns to the equilibrium position without oscillating.
- 235 • **Case 3:** a fractionally damped case ($\alpha = 0.6$) with low stiffness ($k = k_{\text{ref}}$) and high damping
 236 ($c = 100c_{\text{ref}}$) so that the system returns to its original position oscillating around a variable
 237 equilibrium position.

238 • **Case 4:** a fractionally damped case ($\alpha = 0.6$) with high stiffness ($k = 10k_{\text{ref}}$) and low damping
 239 ($c = c_{\text{ref}}$), in which the movement is a combination of the rigid body motion and the first modes
 240 of the system.

241 The four cases are simulated for a time $T = 1$ s using 1000 samples and discretising the shaft
 242 with 60 beam elements. In order to analyse the difference between the cases, the displacement of the
 243 right end, to which a vertical displacement of 3 mm is imposed in the first instant, is plotted over time
 244 (Figure 13).

Figure 13. Displacement of the right end of the shaft: (a) case 1, (b) case 2, (c) case 3, (d) case 4.

245 The first case represents the classical vibration damped in time: this behaviour can be modelled
 246 both with a viscous and a fractional damper. The motion of the second case, instead, is characteristic
 247 of a overdamped system and only achievable if the damping is viscous: a fractionally damped system
 248 will always oscillate, even if the response does not have to necessarily change sign, as the third case
 249 makes clear. Finally, the fourth case represents a more general situation in which the response consists
 250 of a combination of several modes and the rigid body motion. In this case, by tuning the stiffness and
 251 damping parameters and the order of the derivative, different behaviours can be reproduced.

252 The evolution of the shaft in time can be seen in the four videos provided as supplementary
 253 material with this article.

254 4. Conclusions

255 This work discusses the behaviour of a 1 DOF system with fractional damping from the point of
 256 view of dynamics, specially focusing in the divergence of such a model of damping from a classical
 257 viscous one.

258 The first difference between a system with viscous and a fractional damping is that the poles of
 259 the latter are always complex conjugates, which implies that the response is always oscillatory and
 260 that, therefore, the concept of critical damping as defined for viscous systems is not applicable. Also,
 261 due to the viscoelastic nature of fractional damping, the damped frequency of the system decreases
 262 with the order of the derivative, as the system resembles more a pure viscous system, but increases
 263 with the damping parameter, as the contribution to the stiffness of the system increases too.

264 Several particularities can be observed regarding the time response as well. First, the response to
 265 initial conditions is characterised by the appearance of a non oscillatory term, which can be understood

as a change in the position of the equilibrium position in time. Secondly, the response to an impulse allows to define critical damping for this kind of systems as the amount of damping needed for the response not to change its sign. Finally, the response to a step function is characterised by its reduced overshoot but longer settling time is comparison to a system with viscous damping.

Despite their peculiarities, fractional models are useful to ease the modelling process and replicate behaviours that would otherwise require complex formulations. This is the case, for example, of the bearing support represented in this work with a spring and fractional damper for which behaviours that range from a traditional viscous case to an oscillating case with variable equilibrium position can be represented with a single model.

As a final remark, it should be taken into account that a fractional model is a mathematical artifact that, most times, is used to simplify the modelling process. It is advisable, then, to check if the behaviour of the mechanical system under study follows the same trends as the assumed model, or at least, that the effects attributable to the model do not interfere in the computations.

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